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Analysis of the Influence of Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment, and Job Satisfaction on the Performance of Employees of the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the Influence of Leadership, Motivation, Incentives, Work Environment, and Job Satisfaction on the Performance of Employees of the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province. The study used quantitative methods and descriptive analysis of primary and secondary data using questionnaires, documentation, literature studies and direct observation, the number of samples was 100 people through simple random sampling techniques using multiple linear regression as an analysis tool. The results of the study showed that partially leadership had a positive but insignificant or indirect effect on employee performance, competence and work environment had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, as well as simultaneously showing the results that leadership, motivation and incentives in the work environment had a very positive and significant effect on employee performance of the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province. It is recommended that the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province in the future should continue to maintain and improve the competence of its employees, including by conducting courses/training related to the technical field of forestry considering the influence of competence on employee performance which is very significant and positive, it should continue to maintain and improve the quality of the work environment considering the positive and significant influence of the work environment on employee performance.

Keywords: Leadership, motivation, work environment, job satisfaction

Introduction

Performance associated with motivation, leadership, job satisfaction is a concern for researchers in the field of human resources. Financial management requires reliable human resources to be able to plan, administer, implement and carry out accountability. These changes are prerequisites that may be met, internally in the management of Administrative Management and services that can be optimized at the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Service. Without the support of the quality of human resources involved in it, such as the role of leaders towards subordinates, it will affect the success or failure of a goal. Leaders are central figures who can improve the performance of their subordinates.

Based on the results of the inspection data of the North Sulawesi Provincial Inspectorate regarding the overall performance of the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Service which is stated in the form of a value ranging from 0 to 100. Based on the results of the evaluation of the Performance Accountability of the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Service in 2021 and 2022, the scores were "68.70" and "71.86". This value is an accumulation of assessments of all components of performance management that were evaluated, consisting of:

Table 1. Components of performance management evaluation

No.	Component	Weight	2021 Values	2022 Value
1.	Performance Planning	30	21.11	22.20
2.	Performance Measurement	30	23.05	24.00
3.	Reporting Performance	15	10.54	10.65
4.	Evaluation Internal	25	14.00	15.00
Amount		100	68.70	71.86

Source: e-Lakip Inspectorate of North Sulawesi, 2023

Research purposes

1. To analyze the influence of leadership, motivation, incentives, work environment and job satisfaction together on employee performance.
2. To analyze the influence of leadership on employee performance.
3. To analyze the influence of motivation on employee performance.
4. To analyze the influence of the work environment on employee performance.
5. To analyze the influence of job satisfaction on employee performance.

Literature Reviews

Human resource management is seen as a fairly important role in the industrial realm. What human resource management does illustrates how human resource management is activated in the organizational environment. Human resource management is a process that includes evaluating human resource needs, getting people to meet those needs and optimizing the use of these important resources by providing appropriate incentives and assignments, to suit the needs and goals of the organization where the human resources are located (Widodo, 2015: 2).

According to Mangkunegara (2017: 2), Human resource management is a management and utilization of resources that exist in individuals. The management and utilization are developed optimally in the world of work to achieve organizational goals and individual employee development. Human resource management is a science that

studies how to empower employees in organizations, create jobs, work groups, develop employees who have abilities, identify an approach to be able to develop employee performance and reward them for their efforts and work (Bohlander and Snell, 2010: 4).

Performance

Performance is the overall result of work in terms of quantity and quality that has been done by an employee in achieving the goals of an institution or agency. Performance variables are measured or assessed by indicators of quantity and quality of work results. Without good performance at all levels of the organization, achieving goals and organizational success becomes something that is very difficult to achieve.

According to Sutrisno (2016), performance is the result of employee work seen from the aspects of quality, quantity, work time, and cooperation to achieve predetermined goals. According to Afandi (2018), performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with the authority and responsibility given. According to Kasmir (2016), performance is the result of work and work behavior that has been achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given.

Leadership

Leadership is an effort to influence many people through communication to achieve goals, how to influence people with instructions or commands, actions that cause others to act or respond and cause positive change, important dynamic forces that motivate and coordinate organizations in order to achieve goals, the ability to create self-confidence and support among subordinates so that organizational goals can be achieved. Leadership is a science that comprehensively examines how to direct, influence, and supervise others to carry out tasks according to planned orders (Fahmi, 2016).

Motivation

According to Sutrisno, (2009) said that every motivation theory tries to describe what humans really are and what humans can be like. For this reason, it can be said that a motivation theory has content in the form of a certain view of humans. This motivation theory also helps managers and employees to solve problems in the organization. No organization can succeed without a certain level of commitment and effort from its members.

Work environment

The work environment is a very important component when employees carry out work activities. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to work optimally. According to Desi (2015) the Work Environment is all the tools and materials faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and his work arrangements both as individuals and as a group.

Job satisfaction

Basically, job satisfaction is something that is individual. Job satisfaction is a worker's feeling towards his/her job, whether happy or like or not happy or not as a result of the worker's interaction with his/her work environment or as a perception of mental attitude, also as a result of the worker's assessment of his/her job. The worker's feeling towards his/her job reflects his/her attitude and behavior in working (Priansa, 2017).

Previous research

Lengkong et al., (2016) in a study entitled *The Influence of Organizational Communication and Job Stress on Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on Employee Performance at the Public Company Bulog Regional Division of North Sulawesi*. The results of the study concluded that Organizational Communication does not have an effect on Job Satisfaction, Job Stress has an effect on Job Satisfaction, Organizational

Communication and Job Satisfaction have an effect on Employee Performance and Job Stress does not have an effect on Employee Performance at Perum Bulog Divre North Sulawesi.

Trang et al., (2019) in a study entitled The Effect of Workload, Job Stress and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at Gran Puri Hotel. The results of the study showed that simultaneously workload, job stress and job satisfaction influenced employee performance, partially workload and job stress had a negative and significant effect on employee performance, while job satisfaction had a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Tumbuan et al., (2015) in a study entitled The Influence of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance at 21cineplex Manado. The results of this study found the influence of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance at 21Cineplex Manado. Extrinsic Motivation is more important than Intrinsic Motivation.

Tewal et al., (2021) in a study entitled The Influence of Work-Family Conflict on Job Satisfaction and Job Performance of Banking Employees in North Sulawesi. The results of the study showed that work-family conflict had a negative effect on job satisfaction and job performance of banking employees in North Sulawesi. Other results showed that job satisfaction had a significant effect on employee work performance.

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Results of Theoretical and Empirical Studies, 2024

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that leadership, motivation, work environment and job satisfaction simultaneously influence employee performance.

H2: It is suspected that leadership has a partial influence on employee performance.

H3: It is suspected that motivation has a partial effect on employee performance.

H4: SuspectedThe work environment partially influences employee performance.

H5: SuspectedJob satisfaction partially influences employee performance.

Methodology

This study uses a quantitative method with data collection through questionnaires distributed to all employees of the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Office. Data analysis was carried out using multiple linear regression to determine the relationship between variables.

Location and Place of Research

The location of this research was conducted at the Regional Forestry Service Office of North Sulawesi Province.

Method of collecting data

Data was collected through: Direct observation, Questionnaires, and Documentation.

Population and Research Sample

The research population consisted of all employees of the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Service Office and a sample of 100 people taken randomly.

Data analysis

The analysis technique used in this study is multiple regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis is used to determine cause and effect by determining Performance (Y) as the dependent variable and Leadership (X1), Motivation (X2), Work Environment (X3) and Job Satisfaction (X4), as independent variables.

$$Y = B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + B_4X_4 + B_5X_5 + e$$

Information :

Y : Employee performance

B_i : Parameter coefficient for each variable X (i = 1,2,3,4,5)

X₁ : Leadership

X₂ : Motivation

X₃ : Work environment

X₄ : Job satisfaction

E : error

Research Instruments

Data collection techniques by submitting a list of questions in writing with the Research Instrument Scale, each instrument item using the Likert scale has levels from very positive to negative that can be expressed in words. Numbering is done by giving the number one for the smallest object, then the number two for the second object, and so on (Riduwan, 2019).

Results and Discussion

Variable Description

Respondents' description of the research variables includes respondents' assessment of leadership, motivation, work environment, job satisfaction. To determine the intensity of each research variable, a scale range is used which is calculated using the formula:

$$RS = \frac{M - N}{k}$$

Information:

RS : Scale Range

m : maximum score (5)

n : minimum score (1)

k : Number of Categories

Respondent assessment categories for research variables can be explained as follows:

- 1.00 – 1.80 :very low
- 1.81 – 2.60 :low
- 2.61 – 3.40 :currently
- 3.41 – 4.20 :tall

4.21 – 5.00 :very high

Description of Respondents' Assessment of Leadership

The results in this table show that even though leaders have made decisions in accordance with the available information, they have not provided sufficient encouragement to employees.

Table 2. Respondents' Assessment of Leadership

Indicator	Respondent Assessment					Amount	Average
	STS=1	TS=2	N=3	S=4	SS=5		
Ability to give encouragement	2	13	9	55	21	380	3.80
Ability to be accountable for work	1	2	6	73	18	405	4.05
Ability to give directions	1	13	4	63	19	386	3.86
Listening skills	1			72	27	424	4.24
Ability to use information in decision making	1		3	55	41	435	4.35
Ability to determine organizational policies	1	2	6	72	19	406	4.06
Ability to determine organizational strategy	1	1	7	71	20	408	4.08
Ability to negotiate with other departments/companies	1		6	77	16	407	4.07
Ability to run an organization consistently	1		3	70	26	420	4.20
Average Leadership Score							4.08

Description: STS=Strongly Disagree; TS=Disagree; N=Neutral; S=Agree; Strongly Agree

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Description of Respondents' Assessment of Motivation

These results show that the motivation to achieve is higher than the motivation to compete and rule. As shown in the following table;

Table 3. Respondents' Assessment of Motivation

Indicator	Respondent Assessment				Amount	Average
	TS=2	N=3	S=4	SS=5		
Achievement motivation		12	68	20	408	4.08
Affiliate motivation	10	20	56	14	374	3.74
Competition motivation	7	15	68	10	381	3.81
Motivation to rule	2	11	71	16	401	4.01
Average Motivation score						3.91

Description: TS=Disagree; N=Neutral; S=Agree; Strongly Agree

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Description of Respondents' Assessment of the Work Environment

These results indicate that work relationships with coworkers greatly influence the work environment to achieve higher performance than health requirements. As can be seen in the following table;

Table 4. Description of Respondents' Assessment of the Work Environment

Indicator	Respondent Assessment				Amount	Average
	TS=2	N=3	S=4	SS=5		
Working relationship with management		4	71	25	421	4.21
Working relationships with coworkers		2	67	31	429	4.29
The existence of a work security program		23	69	8	385	3.85
Meet health requirements	4	26	60	10	376	3.76
Average Work Environment score						4.03

Description:

TS=Disagree; N=Neutral; S=Agree; Strongly Agree

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Description of Respondents' Assessment of Job Satisfaction

These results indicate that the relationship between job satisfaction with the organization and its work greatly influences performance than the work situation. As obtained in the following table;

Table 5. Description of Respondents' Assessment of Job Satisfaction

Indicator	Respondent Assessment				Amount	Average
	TS=2	N=3	S=4	SS=5		
Satisfaction with awards	3	16	74	7	385	3.85
Satisfaction with work situation	4	51	39	6	347	3.47
Satisfaction with supervision and management	1	26	63	10	382	3.82
Satisfaction with communication between superiors and coworkers	2	31	60	7	372	3.72
Satisfaction with the organization's philosophy and policies	4	17	75	4	379	3.79
Satisfaction with the organization and one's work		5	84	11	406	4.06
Average Job Satisfaction Score						3.79

Description: TS=Disagree; N=Neutral; S=Agree; Strongly Agree

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Description of Respondents' Assessment of Performance

Description of respondents' assessment of performance is an explanation of the relationship between indicators in the questionnaire with the weight of respondents' assessment. Job satisfaction variables are considered high by respondents, namely:

Table 6. Description of Respondents' Assessment of Performance

Indicator	Respondent Assessment					Amount	Average
	STS=1	TS=2	N=3	S=4	SS=5		
Leadership			2	79	19	417	4.17
Motivation			2	78	20	418	4.18
Work environment			4	83	13	409	4.09
Job satisfaction		5	17	66	12	385	3.85
Employee Performance	1	1	1	66	31	425	4.25
Average Performance Score							4.11

Description: TS=Disagree; N=Neutral; S=Agree; Strongly Agree
Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

Validity Test

Validity test is used to measure the level of suitability or ability of indicators or question items in measuring research variables. Validity test is conducted using the Pearson Correlation method. The indicator is valid if the correlation value is greater than 0.5.

Validity of the Leadership variable indicator (X1)

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Value of Leadership Variables

Indicator	Critical Value	Pearson Correlation	Information
Ability to give encouragement	0.5	.529**	Valid
Ability to take responsibility for work	0.5	.824**	Valid
Ability to give directions	0.5	.672**	Valid
Listening skills	0.5	.745**	Valid
Ability to use information in decision making	0.5	.749**	Valid
Ability to determine organizational policies	0.5	.689**	Valid
Ability to determine organizational strategy	0.5	.729**	Valid
Ability to negotiate with other departments/companies	0.5	.730**	Valid
Ability to run an organization consistently	0.5	.726**	Valid

Source: Data Processing Results, 2023

The correlation value of all indicators to the total value is greater than 0.5. This result shows that all valid indicators are able to measure leadership variables. This result shows that even though leaders have made decisions according to the available information, they have not given enough encouragement to employees.

Validity of the Motivation variable (X2)

Motivation variables consist of 4 question items. The correlation value of all indicators to the total value is greater than 0.5. These results indicate that all valid indicators are able to measure motivation variables, as in the table below shows that all of the 4 question items are valid.

Table 8. Pearson Correlation Value of Motivation Variable

Indicator	Critical Value	Motivation	Information
Achievement motivation	0.5	.520**	Valid
Affiliate motivation	0.5	.822**	Valid
Competition motivation	0.5	.796**	Valid
Motivation to rule	0.5	.722**	Valid

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

Validity of question items for the Work Environment variable (X3)

The Work Environment variable consists of 4 question items. The correlation value of all indicators to the total value is greater than 0.5, explaining that all are valid, as in the following table:

Table 9. Pearson Correlation Values of Work Environment Variables

Indicator	Critical Value	Work environment	Information
Working relationship with management	0.5	.639**	Valid
Working relationships with coworkers	0.5	.740**	Valid
The existence of a work security program	0.5	.751**	Valid
Meet health requirements	0.5	.800**	Valid

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

These results indicate that working relationships with coworkers do not have much influence on the work environment for higher performance than meeting health requirements.

Validity of question items for the Job Satisfaction variable (X4)

Job Satisfaction Variable consists of 5 question items. The correlation value of all indicators to the total value is greater than 0.5, explaining that all are valid, as in the following table:

Table 10. Pearson Correlation Values of Job Satisfaction Variables

Indicator	Critical Value	Job satisfaction	Information
Satisfaction with awards	0.5	.720**	Valid
Satisfaction with work situation	0.5	.650**	Valid
Satisfaction with supervision and management	0.5	.696**	Valid
Satisfaction with communication between superiors and coworkers	0.5	.676**	Valid
Satisfaction with the organization's philosophy and policies	0.5	.559**	Valid
Satisfaction with the organization and one's work	0.5	.506**	Valid

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

Validity of question items for Performance variable (Y)

The Performance Variable consists of 5 question items. The correlation value of all indicators to the total value is greater than 0.5, explaining that all are valid, as in the following table:

Table 11. Pearson Correlation Values of Performance Variables

Indicator	Critical Value	Performance	Information
Leadership	0.5	.745**	Valid
Motivation	0.5	.583**	Valid
Work environment	0.5	.717**	Valid
Job satisfaction	0.5	.592**	Valid
Employee Performance	0.5	.595**	Valid

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

These results indicate that the relationship between work performance and performance does not have as much influence on performance as the influence of leadership.

Reliability Test

The results of the reliability test show that all instruments used in this study are reliable. This is indicated by the alpha coefficient exceeding 0.60.

Table 12. Cronbach Alpha Value

Variables	N	Cronbach's Alpha	Critical Value	Results
Leadership	9	.856	0.6	Reliable
Motivation	4	.693	0.6	Reliable
Work environment	4	.710	0.6	Reliable
Job satisfaction	6	.668	0.6	Reliable
Employee Performance	5	.601	0.6	Reliable

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

Multicollinearity Test

Based on the correlation value between independent variables in table 5.20, below 0.9 means there is no multicollinearity. So all independent variables can be included as research variables.

Table 13. Pearson Correlation values between independent variables

Variables	Leadership	Motivation	Work environment	Job satisfaction
Leadership	1	.179	.255*	.283**
Motivation	.179	1	.518**	.403**
Work environment	.326**	.265**	.131	.104
Job satisfaction	.255*	.518**	1	.479**
Employee Performance	.283**	.403**	.479**	1

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was conducted by testing the model and partial test. The model test was used to determine the influence of the variables Leadership, Motivation, Incentives, Work Environment and Job Satisfaction on the Performance variable.

Model Testing

Model testing is done by F test. A model is said to be good if the F value shows significant. The F value is significant if its significance is less than 0.05.

Table 14. Anova table (b)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	78,359	5	15,672	7,816	.000(a)
Residual	188,481	94	2.005		
Total	266,840	99			

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment, Job Satisfaction.
- b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

These results show that together the variables; Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment, Job Satisfaction affect Performance.

Partial Testing (t-Test)

Partial testing is done with the t-test. A model is said to be good if the t-value shows significance. The t-value is significant if its significance is less than 0.05.

Table 15. Coefficients Table (a)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	10,243	1,907		5,370	.000
Leadership	.005	.037	.013	.135	.893
Motivation	.232	.089	.278	2.605	.011
Work environment	-.033	.109	-.033	-.299	.766
Job satisfaction	.277	.079	.360	3,505	.001

Dependent Variable: Performance

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

Based on the partial test (t-test) above, it shows that the variables of Motivation and Job Satisfaction significantly influence Performance. The variables of Leadership, Motivation and Work Environment do not significantly affect Employee Performance.

Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination is used to measure the ability of independent

variables to explain the variation of dependent variables. The coefficient of determination is indicated by the R value.

Table 16. Determination Table

Model	R	R Square	Adjust R Square	Std. Error of theEstimate
1	.542(a)	.294	.256	1.41602

a Predictors: (Constant), Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment, Job Satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: performance

Data Processing Results Source, 2023

The R value = 0.542 shows that 54% of the variability in the Performance variable is due to variations in the Leadership, Motivation, Incentives, Work Environment and Job Satisfaction variables.

Leadership and Employee Performance

The results of the study show that leadership has no effect on employee performance at the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province, meaning that differences in leadership do not result in changes in employee performance.

Employee Motivation and Performance

From the research results, it shows that motivation influences employee performance at the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province, which means that differences in motivation given to employees will result in changes in employee performance.

Work Environment and Employee Performance

The results of the study indicate that the Work Environment does not affect Employee Performance at the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province, meaning that the provision of a good work environment does not result in changes in Employee Performance. These results indicate that employees remain focused on routine work without being influenced by the work environment.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

From the results of the study, it shows that Job Satisfaction affects Employee Performance at the Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province, which means that job satisfaction obtained by employees will result in changes in Employee Performance. These results indicate that employees will be more focused on routine work influenced by employee job satisfaction.

The results of the study are very interesting to be studied further because the variables that have an influence tend to be related to individual characteristics, namely motivation and satisfaction. Leadership and work environment factors have no influence on employee performance. These results indicate employee apathy. Apathy towards leadership models, and the work environment. However, management needs to pay more attention to employee satisfaction, because it is very possible that the decline in the quality of leadership and the work environment has an influence on the decline in employee satisfaction which will ultimately reduce employee performance

Conclusions

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Leadership, motivation, work environment and job satisfaction simultaneously influence employee performance.
2. KPartial leadership does not affect employee performance.
3. Motivation partially influences employee performance.
4. LThe work environment does not partially affect employee performance.
5. Job satisfaction partially influences employee performance.

Suggestion

1. The Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province needs to increase motivation by providing encouragement of affiliation motivation and motivation to compete. By increasing affiliation motivation and motivation to compete with fellow employees, it is expected that employee performance will improve.
2. The Regional Forestry Service of North Sulawesi Province needs to increase employee satisfaction by improving the existing work situation and improving communication between fellow employees and communication between employees and management.
3. Although leadership and work environment do not affect employee performance, the North Sulawesi Provincial Forestry Service has good leadership quality, which must be maintained and even improved

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